

STRUCTURAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE UNITS THAT CREATED INTERNAL ANTONYMY IN PROVERBS

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Abstract. *Types of antonymy from the structural point of view are among the issues that have been studied in more detail. Nevertheless, this linguistic problem has not yet been fully resolved. In this article, some comments on structural types of antonymy were made.*

Key words: *antonymy, lexeme, simple word, compound word, pair of words, repeated word, phrase, phrase.*

СТРУКТУРНАЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ЕДИНИЦ, СОЗДАВАЮЩИХ ВНУТРЕННЮЮ АНТОНИМИЮ В ПОСЛОВИЦАХ

Аннотация. *Виды антонимии со структурной точки зрения относятся к числу вопросов, которые были изучены более подробно. Тем не менее, эта лингвистическая проблема еще не полностью решена. В данной статье были сделаны некоторые замечания по структурным видам антонимии.*

Ключевые слова: *антонимия, лексема, простое слово, сложное слово, пара слов, повторяющееся слово, фраза, словосочетание.*

Before talking about the structural classification of the units that created internal antonymy in proverbs, it is worth mentioning the linguistic definition of the phenomenon of antonymy, which is still not settled in linguistics.

In most textbooks, manuals, and even fundamental research studies, when the relationship of antonymy is explained, there is a contradiction even within phraseological units. This phenomenon is defined only on the basis of the lexical layer. In particular, in the introduction to the "Annotated dictionary of Uzbek antonyms" co-authored by Sh.Rakhmatullayev et al.: "Words with opposite, opposite meanings are called antonyms: big - small, far - close, left - right, get well - sick, love - like hate"¹, - is explained, but a little later: "The antonymic relationship is not only between words, but also between words and phraseological expressions (hero - when a sparrow sings, his heart melts; coward - as if he has a heart in his heart "good"², - indicates that this phenomenon is not limited only to the lexeme.

Or by Rashid Shukurov, who created a fundamental research source on antonymy, "It proved that any lexical and phraseological units can enter into an antonymic relationship with other

¹Rahmatullaev Sh., Mamatov N., Shukurov R. An explanatory dictionary of antonyms of the Uzbek language:- T.: Teacher, 1980. - 232 p. - 7 p.

²Rahmatullaev Sh., Mamatov N., Shukurov R. An explanatory dictionary of antonyms of the Uzbek language:- T.: Teacher, 1980. - 232 p. - 12 b.

lexical units of the same language"³ is called. However, although this author elaborates on a number of issues such as semantic, structural, and material structure specific to the phenomenon of antonymy, this linguistic phenomenon is not given a clear scientific definition.

Of opposition despite the fact that a number of research works have been carried out on its various forms, it can be observed that in the majority of modern educational sources, antonymy is still defined only within the lexical layer. Therefore, in the educational literature co-authored by Rana Saufullaeva and others, which is considered the main textbook for students of higher education institutions studying Uzbek linguistics today: "Antonymy is the relationship of contradiction between lexemes: [big] - [small], [young] - [old], [dwarf] - [huge], [white] - [black], etc."⁴, - is defined as, and no information is given about other forms of antonymy.

In most sources, when enumerating the types of antonyms, lexical, phraseological and affixal ones are mentioned. However, syntactic antonyms are also mentioned in the "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" and "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan".

"Antonymy is the phenomenon of semantically contradicting, opposing language units:

Lexical antonymy. Affixal antonymy. Syntactic antonymy. Antonyms: mutually contradictory, contradictory phrases: high - low, far - close, good - bad (lexical antonyms); -li, -siz: watery - waterless (antonymous affixes); to remember - from memory raise, open-hearted - dark-hearted (phraseological antonyms)"⁵.

"Antonyms (anti ... and wool. onoma - name, name) - language units with opposite meanings. There are 3 types: 1) lexical A. (high - low, long - short); 2) affixal A. (watery - waterless); 3) syntactic A. (open face - tund bashara)"⁶.

But until now, in the special scientific researches carried out in this direction, the existence of syntactic antonymy has not been discussed. 2023 "Lingual and non-linguistic means of expressing opposition in the Uzbek language" by Orinboyeva E'zozkhan"⁷" one chapter of his thesis submitted for the degree of doctor of philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences is called "Expression of opposition relation at the syntactic level". However, it is not about the word combinations, but about the contrast between the parts of the compound sentence.

In our opinion, just as there is an antonymy relationship between lexical, phraseological, and affixal units, contradictions can also appear within word combinations. Take, for example, the good job - bad job or good person - bad person pairings.

The first couplet *good deed is a bad deed* structured in the style The meaning of these phrases:

³Shukurov R. The lexical-semantic nature of the antonyms of the Uzbek language: Philol. science. name ... diss. - T., 1973. - 155 p. - 55 p.

⁴Saufullaeva R., Mengliyev B., Bakiyeva G., Qurbonova M., Yunusova Z., Abuzalova M. Current Uzbek literary language: - T., 2009. - 414 p. - 113 p.

⁵Hojiev A. Explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms: - T.: National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2002. - 165 p. - 14 p.

⁶National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Letter A: - T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. - 879 p. - 560 p. <https://n.ziyouz.com/kutubkhona/category/11-o-uzbekistan-milliy-encyclopedia>

⁷Orinboyeva E. Linguistic and non-linguistic means of expressing opposition in the Uzbek language: Filol.fan. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) diss... - Fergana, 2023. - 142 p.

-work that has a positive quality, that meets a requirement, that is pleasing to a person, that meets a requirement;

- unpleasant, unpleasant work.

It is true that the differential meaning is created by good and bad lexemes, but they express this content only when they are combined with the working lexeme.

Now a good person is a bad person if we pay attention to the pair, we can see that good and bad lexemes are manifested in other themes, i.e.:

- a person with a negative character;

- immoral, bad-tempered, corrupt person.

A good lexeme 5-volume oin the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language:

1. Having a positive quality, satisfying a requirement, pleasing to a person, satisfying a requirement.

2. Consent means approval: it comes in the meanings of okay, true, acceptable. Bad lexeme has 14 different meanings. Their meaning can be determined in the context, in most cases in the process that created the phrase.

As phraseological units create antonymy with each other and with lexemes, word combinations can create a similar situation of opposition. For example, *liar* and a man of right words there is a contradiction between the lexeme and the meaning expressed through a chain of complex word combinations. This case can also prove that there is an antonymic relationship in the structure of word combinations.

As L.A. Novikov noted: "Anonym is a component of the content of the word. It appears as an important characteristic of the lexical meaning, a special expression of differentiation in the language, an opposition of the objects of the objective world.⁸,- taking into account that antonymy works with the content plan, we consider a word combination expressing a concept such as a lexeme and a phrase as a linguistic unit that creates this relationship. That's right, a word combination is a grammatical phenomenon, a speech unit, the parts of which can be freely replaced. But the meaning understood through it represents a semantic whole. From this point of view, we believe that it is necessary to scientifically investigate the possibilities related to the content plan of the proud event. In the scientific research, we looked at the phenomenon of antonymy as a specific aspect of this process and tried to shed light on its possibilities related to the textual, especially the structural aspect of proverbs.

"The lexical-semantic nature of antonyms in the Uzbek language" by Rashid Shukurov, which is considered one of the best studies on antonymy.⁹more than thirty types of structurally antonymic lines (with variants) are distinguished in the research work.

Based on this research We structurally classify the units that create internal antonymy in proverbs as follows and enrich it on the basis of word combinations:

Antonyms of lexemes

Antonym of components in the form of a simple root word

⁸Novikov L.A. Antonyms in the Russian language - M., 1973. - S. 59.

⁹ Shukurov R. The lexical-semantic nature of the antonyms of the Uzbek language: Philol. science. name ... diss. - T.: 1973. - 113 p.

1. Antonyms in the form of root word + root word: A man is born for himself, he dies for his wife; Lie on the threshold of good before you lie in the net of evil.
2. Antonyms in the form of root word + simple artificial word: Out of a thousand beautiful words, one ugly deed is better. Knowledge is light, ignorance is darkness; Do not pass by the liar, do not pass by the truth. A brave man does not shop, a coward does not run away.
3. Antonyms in the form of root word + compound word: He says he will burn poor until he says he will be rich.
4. Antonyms in the form of root word + pair of words: The leader comes and goes, the masses stay.
5. Antonyms in the form of root word + repeated word: Don't say the river is slow, if it flows often, you will drown.
6. Root word + antonyms in the form of a phrase: Walking alone until you find your way, wandering with many; Your country is your death bed, your cradle that cannot be another country
Antonym of simple artificial components
7. Antonyms in the form of simple passive + passive passive:
 - a) Antonyms with the same stem in the form simple artificial + simple artificial¹⁰
A person with knowledge, a person without knowledge; Knowledge is light, anonymity is darkness.
 - b) Antonyms in the form of simple artificial + simple artificial words with different stems: Science - light, anonymity - darkness; He who is stingy to himself is not generous to others; Good - honorable, bad - honorable.
8. Antonyms in the form of simple verb + compound word: The work of the zealous is successful, the eyes of the unmotivated are closed; Be the happy bride of the poor until the rich man's happiness is his black wife.
9. Simple construction + antonyms in the form of a pair of words: A rich man's sweet food is better than a poor man's tasteless porridge.
10. Antonyms in the form of simple + repeated words: Your tasteless food is better than your sweet words.
11. Simple phrase + phrasal verb: Inexhaustible, miserly - a cloud can't see its smoke
Antonyms of compound words
12. Compound word + antonyms in the form of compound word: Be a fool with many until you are wise alone; You can say "come" but you can't say "go".
Desiredenough, the jealous one will lose.
13. Antonyms in the form of a compound word + a pair of words: They laugh at the poor man's sober son, they laugh at the rich man's lazy son.
14. Antonyms in the form of a compound word + repeated word: To be a man gradually, to be an animal in one step.
15. Compound word + antonyms in the form of a phrase: The good will be kind, the bad will draw blood from the whip

¹⁰"An explanatory dictionary of antonyms of the Uzbek language" was used as a basis for this issue, as it is a controversial issue whether the lexemes formed with the help of antonyms can form an antonym relationship.

Antonym of pairs of words

16. Pair of words + antonyms in the form of a pair of words: He who has tasted bitter and sweet, he has walked near and far; There is no time to learn; If you talk sweetly, get out of the snake's den. If you speak bitterly, leave the Muslim religion; When you dig and laugh, you water.

17. Antonyms in the form of a pair of words + repeated words: The threshing floor, which is often gathered, is slowly exhausted.

18. Pair of words + antonyms in the form of a phrase: Better than a rich relative, better than a barefoot neighbor.

Antonyms of repeated words

19. Repeated word + repeated antonyms in the form of words: When you dig a ditch crying, you drink water playfully; Eating a little is good, eating a lot is bad; If you give her to a good place, she will become a sultan. If you give the girl to a bad place, he will make you angry; When they say "Take it", believe it. When they say "Give-give", don't be restless.

20. Repeated word + antonyms in the form of phrasal verbs: Work that starts slowly is done in the blink of an eye.

Antonyms of phrases

21. Phrases + antonyms in the form of phrasal verbs: A good leader leads the way, a bad leader corrupts the way; He does not know how to see evil, he does not know how to see well; A good wish leads to perfection, a bad wish leads to misery.

Antonym of the components of a phrase

22. Antonyms in the form of word combination + word combination: A straight-grown flower will be, a crooked-grown ash will be; The one who joins the hand is sad, the one who is separated from the hand has no face; *The harm of evil* but the good is in the narrow way;

The work of the good - heaven, the work of the bad - punishment; A capable son mounts a horse, an incompetent (son) dismounts; The mouth of the one who has money plays, the eyes of the one who has no money play.

23. Word combination + antonyms in the form of a simple root word: a simple person - a trickster, a trickster; belonging to all-private, from cash, you win, you wait for a loan; He gives a lot of money, but the poor does not get it;

24. Word combination + antonyms in the form of a simple artificial word: There is no shame in a liar, no shame in a truthful person;

25. Word combination + antonyms in the form of a compound word: A crooked tree does not grow straight; A good leader brings joy to the country, an ignorant leader brings a "guest" to the country.

26. Phrase + antonyms in the form of a pair of words: A noisy hut is better than a quiet house.

27. Word combination + antonyms in the form of a repeated word: A little is unknown, a large amount is not closed; A sack for those who work, an empty sack for those who don't.

28. Word combination + antonyms in the form of a phrase: Let the blood of a hero bleed, let the soul of a coward bleed; When he speaks to himself, let him be silent with a short hand;

Better than a greedy miser, an open heart is better; *Darkness of the face* not shame, blackness is shame (formation).

It seems that word combinations have equal opportunities as lexeme and phraseme in terms of structure in forming an antonymic series. This is also an example of the existence of antonymy of word combinations.

29. Tell based on observations It is possible that the units that created internal antonymy in proverbs are structurally equivalent to simple words and word combinations. In general, it can be seen that all types of structurally antonymic series listed by Rashid Shukurov are easily used in proverbs. But the same components: simple word + simple word; compound word + compound word; phrasal verb + phrasal verb; double word + double word; repeated word + repeated word; antonymic pairs in the form of phrase + phrase are more common than those with different structures.

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